

ENCORPORATING SUSTAINABILITY 5.0 TO PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Project sustainability refers to the continuation of a project's outcomes and benefits even after its completion. This means ensuring that the project's outputs continue to serve their intended purpose, that their multiplier effects are monitored, and that the project's full potential is maintained throughout and beyond its lifecycle. This study explores the development and implementation of a project sustainability strategy, using the Horizon Europe-funded project, SMART4ENV, as a case study. It examined how a robust sustainability framework ensures that project outcomes and benefits persist beyond the project's formal completion. This is particularly critical for research and R&D initiatives, where outputs like scientific discoveries can spur new collaborations, ventures, and subsequent advancements, thereby creating lasting value for both the scientific and economic communities. Our methodology incorporated a combination of the Analytic Network Process (ANP) and the Green Project Management P5 Standard to integrate the perspectives of project partners into a cohesive strategy for the SMART4ENV legacy. The framework was informed by a review of relevant academic literature and best practices from previous Horizon-funded projects. We gathered both qualitative and quantitative data through collaborative workshops with project partners, using online co-creation sessions.

The resulting sustainability strategy, developed during the project's initiation, functioned as a "living document" throughout the execution phase. It was continuously refined using both feedback and feedforward mechanisms to adapt to evolving needs and challenges. Our findings indicate that integrating a sustainability strategy early in the project design, along with continuous improvement loops, significantly facilitates the long-term exploitation of project results and enhances the overall efficiency of grant funding. However, we also identified challenges, such as the difficulty of managing stakeholder involvement and aligning with long-term corporate strategies, as these factors often lie beyond the direct control of the project team and the beneficiary organization.

Keywords: Sustainability, Project Management, ANP, GPM